

Aeroacoustic Characteristics of a Twin-Propeller Distributed Electric Propulsion System with Phase Synchronisation at Various Wing Angles of Attack

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The noise emission of future distributed electric propulsion (DEP) concepts has been a primary concern throughout the design process. This work focuses on experimentally and numerically examining the noise produced by a leading-edge-mounted twin-propeller DEP system with phase-controlled two-bladed 9-inch propellers, at various wing angles of attack (AoAs). The experiments were conducted in the University of Bristol Wind Tunnel, complemented by mid-fidelity numerical simulations. The results show that the sensitivity of the first blade passing frequency tonal noise directivity to wing AoA change decreases with decreasing advance ratio J for zero-degree relative phase angles ($\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$). The implementation of propeller relative phase control is shown to effectively reduce tonal noise across all wing AoAs at different propeller advance ratios, although the level of attenuation depends strongly on observer positions and operating conditions. The minimum noise levels are typically achieved at $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ for observer positions representative of the passenger side (top microphone arc), and at $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ for measurement locations aligned with the propeller separation plane (horizontal microphone arc). This behaviour is consistent across the studied range of wing AoA. The numerical predictions using the vortex particle method (VPM) successfully captured the overall directivity trends and relative phase effects, although a consistent underprediction of sound pressure level (SPL) was observed on the top microphone arc. These results demonstrate that propeller phase control can effectively mitigate tonal noise in DEP systems at non-zero AoA, while further model refinement is needed to improve predictive accuracy under complex inflow conditions.

I. Nomenclature

c	=	wing chord length
D	=	propeller diameter
J	=	propeller advance ratio
P/D	=	pitch-to-diameter ratio
s	=	propeller hub-to-hub distance
α	=	wing angle of attack (AoA)
$\Delta\psi$	=	propeller relative phase angle
θ	=	observer position on the top arc
ϕ_{pp}	=	power spectral density (PSD) of acoustic pressure
φ	=	observer position on the horizontal arc
p_{ref}	=	reference acoustic pressure (20 μPa)
V_∞	=	freestream velocity
Ω	=	propeller angular velocity

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Γ_p	=	circulation strength of vortex particle p
ν	=	kinematic viscosity
r_c	=	vortex core radius
ρ	=	air density
AoA	=	angle of attack
BPF	=	blade passing frequency
DEP	=	distributed electric propulsion
ESC	=	electronic speed controller
PSD	=	power spectral density
RPM	=	revolutions per minute
SPL	=	sound pressure level
UAM	=	urban air mobility
VLM	=	vortex lattice method
VPM	=	vortex particle method

II. Introduction

The distributed electric propulsion (DEP) concept has been one of the most popular and intriguing designs in recent years, dedicated to not only next-generation larger mainline aircraft, but also smaller urban air mobility (UAM) and eVTOL aircraft developments [1, 2]. Typically, the DEP system involves an array of electrical propulsors that are directly connected to the power sources, which reduces the mechanical complexities of the traditional aircraft. As of now, the DEP systems with leading-edge mounted propellers have proven their capabilities to improve the aircraft aerodynamic efficiency through experimental and numerical approaches [3–9]. For example, Lee et al. [3] experimentally investigated the aerodynamic flow field of a four-propeller rectangular wing and found that the propeller slipstream significantly increased the maximum lift coefficient and lift-curve slope by accelerating the flow over the wing and delaying flow separation. Ma et al. [7] recently developed a wing-propeller interaction model and compared the aerodynamic performance between single propeller conventional configurations and DEP configurations with up to four propellers on the semi-span. They concluded that the DEP aircraft achieves about 6% greater range than the conventional setup, and the four-propeller configuration demonstrated minimal induced drag due to the tip-mounted propeller counteracting the wing-tip vortex.

Noise emitted from the DEP system is different from traditional aircraft configurations, usually considered to be quieter because of the multi-propulsor design dividing up the total thrust required and hence reducing the tip speed of the propeller [10, 11]. Understanding the physical mechanisms that govern noise generation is essential for UAM systems, particularly under hover and forward-flight conditions. Previous works have been examining the noise characteristics of all components in the DEP system, including the propeller-propeller interaction [12, 13] and propeller-wing interaction [5, 14, 15]. De Paola et al. [5] investigated the relationship between the tonal noise at the first blade passing frequency (BPF) and the angles of attack (AoAs) of the wing for a three-propeller DEP configuration. They observed that apart from the noise level at the first BPF, there is an apparent increment in both the tonal and broadband noise components on the wing pressure side when the wing angle of attack increases, primarily because of the interaction between the rotor wakes and the wing surface. Turhan et al. [16] found that, for a leading-edge-mounted two-propeller DEP configuration, the farfield noise depends strongly on the propeller advance ratio. At a constant rotational speed of 8000 rpm, increasing the advance ratio reduced the farfield noise. They also noted that a smaller tip clearance of 1% of the propeller diameter generated slightly higher sound pressure level (SPL) at the BPF than a larger clearance of 4%.

Given that the future UAM aircraft featuring DEP concepts will be mainly operating in and near urban environments, the reduction of the noise emitted from the system is vital in developing, designing, and operating the aircraft [17–20]. Approaches for reducing aircraft noise emissions are commonly divided into passive and active strategies. Passive techniques aim to modify the physical design, such as blade geometry, spacing, or airframe configuration, to achieve quieter operation [21]. Active approaches, on the other hand, rely on directly controlling acoustic sources. In DEP systems, each propeller acts as an individual sound source; therefore, coordinated phase control can be used to promote destructive interference and reduce overall noise levels. Such strategies offer promising pathways for mitigating noise in urban environments while improving passenger comfort and public acceptance of DEP-based air transport. The application of the propeller phase synchronisation technique on a DEP system is one of the most well-known measures, which is capable of dramatically reducing the tonal noise, especially at 1st propeller BPF [2, 13, 22–29]. Turhan et al. [29] experimentally investigated the noise reduction that could be achieved by controlling the relative phase angle

of two side-by-side propellers. The farfield acoustic results indicated that increasing the relative phase angle from fully in-phase to fully out-of-phase leads to a significant reduction in the BPF tonal noise that is independent of the observer angle and the propeller advance ratio. Additionally, they examined the correlation between psychoacoustic annoyance and the aeroacoustic characteristics of the DEP system, and found that introducing a relative phase-angle control between the two propellers effectively alleviates psychoacoustic annoyance. Other experimental works on propeller phase synchronisation also provided similar results on tonal noise reduction [22–25]. Analytical and numerical analyses on phase synchronisation techniques were also carried out worldwide [13, 25, 27]. Zarri et al. [13] revealed that proximity-induced aerodynamic interactions generate dominant tonal noise across most spatial directions of a twin-propeller DEP system. This phenomenon arises from two primary mechanisms: time-averaged inflow distortions caused by adjacent propellers, and impulsive local effects at the blade tips, which can be controlled by the relative phase angle between the two propellers. They also noted that, despite the BPF harmonic tone being significantly reduced when propellers operate at a controlled phase angle, the aerodynamic performance of the propeller remains unchanged. This consistency in propeller aerodynamic performance was also confirmed by experimental observations [22, 30].

To date, most studies on noise mitigation in DEP systems through propeller phase synchronisation have been limited to wings operating at 0° AoA. To the best of our knowledge, few comprehensive experimental investigations have explored the combined effects of varying wing AoA and high rotational speeds up to 9000 rpm under phase-synchronised conditions. There remains a notable gap in understanding how the effectiveness of phase control evolves with changes in wing AoA and propeller advance ratio. Therefore, the aim of the present work is to establish a series of experimental test campaigns to investigate the noise characteristics of a twin-propeller DEP system under different wing AoA and propeller relative phase angles, with varying propeller rotational speeds and advance ratios. Mid-fidelity numerical simulations were also carried out to confirm the experimental findings and assess the current model’s noise prediction capability across different wing AoAs and relative phase angles.

The remainder of the paper is as follows: Section III outlines the experimental setup for the DEP configurations and test matrix for this work, followed by the numerical setup used for the mid-fidelity vortex particle method (VPM) simulations. Section IV demonstrates the experimental measurements and numerical VPM predictions on the noise emission of the DEP system under different wing AoAs, propeller advance ratios, and relative phase angles. Finally, Section V provides a summary of the current work and provides outlooks for the potential future works based on findings from this paper.

III. Methodology

A. Experimental Setup.

The aeroacoustic experiments were conducted in the Pressure Neutral Wind Tunnel (PNWT) at the Lawson Wind Tunnel Laboratory, University of Bristol. The PNWT is designed as an open-jet closed-loop facility with a nozzle exit measuring 1 m in length and 0.7 m in width. The nozzle and the test section are located in an acoustically-treated chamber of $4.1 \times 4.5 \times 4$ m, with foam wedges to minimise acoustic reflections. This aeroacoustic facility has been utilised for numerous previous aeroacoustic studies, such as [20, 31, 32]. The open-jet nozzle is capable of producing steady freestream velocities up to $V_\infty = 35$ m/s, with a turbulence intensity of approximately 0.2%.

Figure 1 demonstrates the setup for the twin-propeller DEP configuration. Two microphone arcs were utilised in this work with GRAS 40PL-10 microphones that were calibrated prior to and after each test using a GRAS 42AA pistonphone calibrator. The microphones featured a bandwidth of 10 Hz to 20 kHz, a dynamic range of 142 dB, and an accuracy of ± 1 dB. The top arc (indicated in blue in Fig. 1) measured the noise directivity in the spanwise plane of the DEP setup. Located in the plane of $\varphi = 0^\circ$ in the spherical coordinate system, it consisted of 13 microphones with observer angles between $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\theta = 110^\circ$ in 5° increments. The microphone located at $\theta = 90^\circ$ was directly aligned with the propellers. The horizontal arc (indicated in red in Fig. 1) measured noise emission in the plane of $\theta = 0^\circ$ at the middle of the two propellers, covering observer angles between $\varphi = 55^\circ$ and $\varphi = 110^\circ$, also in 5° increments. Data were sampled at 2^{15} Hz for $t = 32$ s. The SPL is determined using the following equation:

$$SPL = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\phi_{pp}}{p_{ref}^2} \right), \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_{pp} is the power spectral density (PSD) of the measured acoustic pressure, and the reference acoustic pressure p_{ref} is set as $20 \mu\text{Pa}$.

Fig. 1 Schematic of the twin-propeller DEP setup and microphone arc layouts.

The centre of the wing was placed in the middle of the open jet nozzle and positioned approximately 500 mm downstream from the nozzle exit, with the middle of the two propellers aimed at the nozzle centreline. The wing was designed with a NACA 0018 profile and a chord of $c = 0.3$ m and a span of $L = 0.9$ m. It was manufactured using 6000 series aluminium alloy in a 4-axis CNC machine. The propulsion unit included an electronic speed controller (ESC) to drive a brushless motor with a propeller, and incremental encoders were used to monitor and control the motor's rotational speed and the relative phase angle between the two propellers. The phase control algorithm was built in-house in National Instruments LabVIEW, and readers are referred to [33] for further details on the phase controller design and performance. Two T-Motor 2.2 kW AT4125 540 kV motors were utilised. The tests employed two identical two-bladed constant-pitch propellers with diameters of $D = 9$ inches (228.6 mm) and a pitch-to-diameter ratio of $P/D = 1$. These propellers, manufactured by Mejzlik (<https://www.mejzlik.eu/>), were made from carbon fibre/epoxy composite material and featured a Clark-Y aerofoil profile.

Fig. 2 Propeller relative phase angle $\Delta\psi$ and the propeller separation s/D of the twin-propeller DEP system. Both propellers are rotating CCW when viewed from the front.

The relative phase angle $\Delta\psi$ between the two propellers is defined in Fig. 2. The inboard propeller served as the reference propeller; different relative phase angles $\Delta\psi$ are achieved by controlling the blade position of the outboard propeller. Both propellers were rotating counterclockwise (CCW) when viewed from the front. The wing AoA was selected at four different positions: 0° , 5° , 10° , and 15° , and the orientation of the AoA sweep is illustrated in Figure 3(a).

The inflow speed, V_∞ , chosen for the current study was 12 m/s, while the propeller rotational speeds were 5000, 6000, and 9000 rpm. The corresponding advance ratio, J , can then be calculated as:

$$J = \frac{V_\infty}{nD} \quad (2)$$

where n is the rotational speed in revolutions per second, and D is the propeller diameter. The propeller separation is set to $s/D = 1.05$. Figure 3(b) illustrates the DEP test rig setup inside the aeroacoustic chamber.

Fig. 3 Twin-propeller DEP system utilised in this study: (a) wing angle of attack (AoA) α definition, and (b) setup inside the wind tunnel.

B. Mid-Fidelity Aerodynamic and Aeroacoustic Simulation

The coupled aerodynamic and aeroacoustic behaviour of two phase-synchronised propellers operating at a non-zero wing AoA was modelled as illustrated in Fig. 1, using a mid-fidelity computational framework. This framework integrated unsteady potential-flow formulations for aerodynamic prediction with an acoustic analogy for noise radiation. The aerodynamic surfaces were represented through the vortex lattice method (VLM), which discretised thin lifting surfaces into a lattice of quadrilateral vortex-ring elements composed of constant-strength filaments. The induced velocity at a given evaluation point, \mathbf{r}_0 , due to a filament of strength γ and end positions \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 , was obtained from the Biot–Savart law with a finite vortex core correction:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\gamma}{4\pi} \frac{(\|\mathbf{r}_1\| + \|\mathbf{r}_2\|)(\|\mathbf{r}_1\| \|\mathbf{r}_2\| - \mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)}{\|\mathbf{r}_1\| \|\mathbf{r}_2\| (\|\mathbf{r}_1 \times \mathbf{r}_2\|^2 + r_c^2 \|\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1\|^2)}, \quad (3)$$

where $r_c = \sqrt{4\alpha_L \nu \delta t}$ and $\delta = 1 + a_1 \frac{\gamma}{v}$. The flow tangency condition was enforced at the collocation point of each element, forming a linear system that determines the panel strengths from the local induced velocities.

Unlike conventional unsteady VLM or panel approaches, the wake in this formulation was not represented as a deforming sheet of vortex rings. Instead, it was modelled via the vortex particle method (VPM), in which the wake vorticity was discretised into Lagrangian vortex particles convected by the local velocity field. This strategy avoided mesh distortion and entanglement issues that typically arise in configurations with strong wake–wake and wake–surface interactions, such as those generated by multiple propellers or by inflow with incidence. The VPM formulation stemmed from the discretised vorticity transport equation, derived from the incompressible Navier–Stokes equations. Assuming a solenoidal velocity field induced by the particles allowed the use of Green’s function to determine the induced velocity, which could then be superposed with the irrotational velocity from the surface elements following Helmholtz decomposition. The governing VPM scheme used in this work is summarised in Eqns. 4, 5, and 6; detailed derivations can be found in [34–36].

$$\frac{d}{dt}\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_p(t) = (\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_p(t) \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_p(t), t) + \frac{d}{dt}\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_p^{\text{visc}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathbf{x}_p(t) = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_p(t), t) = \sum_q K(\mathbf{x}_p(t), \mathbf{x}_q(t)) \times \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_p(t), \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_p^{\text{visc}} = \frac{105}{4\pi\sigma^5} \sum_q \frac{V_p\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_q - V_q\boldsymbol{\Gamma}_p}{\left[\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{x}_p - \mathbf{x}_q\|}{\sigma}\right)^2 + 1\right]^{\frac{9}{2}}}. \quad (6)$$

where the particle kernel $K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ followed the formulation of Winckelmans and Leonard [35], and viscous diffusion was treated through a Particle Strength Exchange scheme. At each time step, a new row of particles was released from the trailing edge of each aerodynamic surface, with their circulation strengths inherited from the corresponding trailing-edge vortex rings of the previous iteration. Once the aerodynamic solution was obtained, the acoustic field was evaluated using Farassat’s Formulation 1A [37] of the Ffowcs–Williams and Hawkings equation. Both monopole and dipole terms were integrated over the aerodynamic surfaces, while quadrupole sources from the volume were neglected.

For the present configuration, the wing was modelled using 80 spanwise panels with uniform spacing and 16 chordwise panels with cosine clustering on both upper and lower surfaces, totalling 2560 panels. Each two-bladed propeller comprised 41 spanwise and 24 chordwise panels per blade, corresponding to 984 panels per blade or 1968 panels per propeller. The full aerodynamic model, therefore, consisted of 6496 panels. Simulations were conducted at a rotational speed of 5000 rpm for a total of 15 revolutions, corresponding to a physical duration of 0.18 s. The time step, equivalent to a 2° propeller rotation, resulted in 2700 steps of $\Delta t = 6.67 \times 10^{-5}$ s. The evolution of the thrust-aligned force component (F_x) for a previous run (with AoA = 0°) was shown in Fig. 4, illustrating the transient response until steady conditions were reached. The aerodynamic and aeroacoustic data were calculated from the last 10 revolutions—i.e., from revolution 6 to 15 (time interval 0.06–0.18 s)—after confirming convergence of the aerodynamic loads under the imposed inflow angle.

Fig. 4 Time history of component load parallel to the propellers’ axes for the complete setup ($\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$). The vertical dashed line indicates the time from which aerodynamics and noise quantities are calculated.

IV. Results and Discussion

In this section, noise results from the two microphone arcs and numerical VPM predictions are presented. Firstly, the effects of wing AoA change on noise emission for a constant propeller relative phase angle of $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ are investigated. Then, the effectiveness of implementing various relative phase angles at different wing AoAs is illustrated. Finally, comparisons between experimental measurements and numerical VPM simulations are presented to assess the capability of the current VPM model to predict noise characteristics across different wing AoAs and relative phase angles $\Delta\psi$. The propeller advance ratio J for 5000, 6000 and 9000 rpm at $V_\infty = 12$ m/s are 0.63, 0.53 and 0.35, respectively.

Fig. 5 Noise spectra measured at the observer position $\theta = 90^\circ$ on the top arc for $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ at different wing AoAs. Results are shown for (a) $J = 0.63$, (b) $J = 0.53$, and (c) $J = 0.35$. Magnified views of the tonal peaks at the BPF and its second harmonic ($2\times\text{BPF}$) are shown on the right.

A. Effect of wing AoA at constant propeller relative phase angle $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ on noise level.

Figures 5 and 6 show the noise spectra at microphone positions of θ and $\varphi = 90^\circ$ on both arcs at $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$. The propeller-off noise was also measured at each rotational speed at AoA = 0° , with both propellers removed from the motor at an inflow speed of $V_\infty = 12$ m/s. The results show that, in the absence of the propellers, the noise levels are significantly below the tonal levels and do not contribute to any tonal components, as shown by the dotted grey lines. The first BPF of the propeller changes with advance ratio because the inflow velocity is held constant while the rotational speed varies between cases. For the top arc at $J = 0.63$, as shown in Fig. 5(a), the tonal noise level at the first BPF increases as the wing AoA increases. At AoA = 15° , the first BPF tonal level is approximately 9 dB higher than at AoA = 0° . However, this difference between AoA cases decreases as J is reduced. At $J = 0.35$ (see Fig. 5(c)), the effect of AoA on the first BPF tonal level becomes minimal. The $2\times\text{BPF}$ tonal peaks at AoA = 0° and 5° show similar SPL levels across the advance ratios, with differences of approximately 1–2 dB. For AoA = 15° , the $2\times\text{BPF}$ tonal peak is about 3 dB lower than that at AoA = 0° when $J = 0.63$. However, this trend reverses at the lower advance ratio ($J = 0.35$), where AoA = 15° produces slightly higher noise levels than AoA = 0° and 5° (by approximately 2 dB), and up to 8 dB higher compared to AoA = 10° . The broadband noise shows no significant variation with increasing AoA.

Fig. 6 Noise spectra measured at the observer position $\varphi = 90^\circ$ on the horizontal arc for $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ at different wing AoAs. Results are shown for (a) $J = 0.63$, (b) $J = 0.53$, and (c) $J = 0.35$. Magnified views of the tonal peaks at the BPF and its second harmonic ($2\times\text{BPF}$) are shown on the right.

On the other hand, for the spectra at the observer position $\varphi = 90^\circ$ on the horizontal arc, as shown in Fig. 6, the broadband noise level slightly increases as the wing AoA increases, particularly at higher advance ratios of $J = 0.53$ and 0.63 . The tonal noise level at the first BPF for $J = 0.63$ decreases as the wing AoA increases from 0° to 10° , and then increases significantly (by approximately 10 dB) as the AoA further increases to 15° . As the advance ratio decreases, the sensitivity of the first BPF tonal noise to AoA becomes less pronounced, consistent with the trends observed on the top arc. The second harmonic ($2\times\text{BPF}$) exhibits a strong dependence on AoA across all advance ratios on the horizontal arc, indicating that higher-order interaction mechanisms remain sensitive to AoA variations. Nevertheless, the present study focuses primarily on the 1st BPF, as it represents the dominant tonal component in the acoustic signature.

Figure 7 presents the directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise for different wing AoA at three advance ratios, $J = 0.63$, 0.53 , and 0.35 . Measurements on the top arc (left column) and horizontal arc (right column) reveal distinct trends depending on observer location. On the top arc, a consistent and monotonic increase in SPL is observed with increasing AoA for all advance ratios, with AoA = 15° producing the highest noise levels and AoA = 0° the lowest. The directivity pattern is relatively smooth, with SPL gradually increasing with observer angle and peaking around $\theta \approx 90^\circ\text{--}100^\circ$. The influence of AoA is most pronounced at $J = 0.63$, where differences of up to ~ 10 dB are observed, while at

Fig. 7 Directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise measured on the top arc (left column) and horizontal arc (right column) for $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ at different wing AoAs. Results are shown for (a) and (b) $J = 0.63$, (c) and (d) $J = 0.53$, and (e) and (f) $J = 0.35$.

lower advance ratios ($J = 0.35$), the curves converge, indicating reduced sensitivity to inflow angle under high loading conditions. In contrast, the horizontal arc exhibits a more complex and non-monotonic response to changes in AoA, particularly at higher advance ratios. At $J = 0.63$, the tonal noise initially decreases as AoA increases from 0° to 10° , followed by a significant increase at 15° , reaching differences of up to ~ 10 dB depending on the observer angle. At $J = 0.53$, the same trend is observed but is less pronounced. When J further decreases to 0.35, the lowest noise levels are obtained at 15° , indicating behaviour that differs from that at higher advance ratios.

Figure 8 compares the directivity of the first BPF tonal noise measured on the top and horizontal microphone arcs for different advance ratios at all four wing AoAs. In general, variations in wing AoA do not significantly alter the overall shape of the directivity curves across the microphone arcs. The noise level is strongly dependent on advance ratio, with the highest SPL consistently observed at the lowest advance ratio ($J = 0.35$) for both microphone arcs. For the top arc measurements shown in the left column of Fig. 8, the highest SPL occurs at $J = 0.35$, while the lowest SPL is observed at $J = 0.63$. For the horizontal arc results illustrated in the right column of Fig. 8, a similar trend is observed. At all AoAs, $J = 0.35$ produces the highest noise levels, whereas $J = 0.63$ and $J = 0.53$ exhibit similar behaviour.

Until now, the analysis has focused on noise levels at a constant relative phase angle in order to isolate and examine the effects of wing AoA, directivity, and advance ratio. This approach allows the individual influence of each parameter on the tonal noise characteristics to be clearly identified. In the following section, different relative phase angles are compared to evaluate the effectiveness of phase-based noise reduction under varying operating conditions. This comparison provides further insight into how phase synchronisation can be utilised to minimise tonal noise across a range of advance ratios, observer locations, and AoAs.

Fig. 8 Directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise measured on the top arc (left column) and horizontal arc (right column) for $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ at different advance ratios, J . Results are shown for (a) and (b) $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, (c) and (d) $\text{AoA} = 5^\circ$, (e) and (f) $\text{AoA} = 10^\circ$, and (g) and (h) $\text{AoA} = 15^\circ$.

B. Effect of wing AoA on 1st BPF tonal noise attenuation with propeller relative phase controls.

1. Tonal noise directivity on the top arc.

Figure 9 illustrates the tonal noise directivity patterns with propeller relative phase angles $\Delta\psi$ for all wing AoAs measured on the top arc at $J = 0.53$ and $J = 0.35$. At $J = 0.53$, as shown in the left column of Fig. 9, the tonal noise reduction of applying $\Delta\psi < 45^\circ$ is around less than 5 to 7 dB compared to the 0° relative phase angle case at all four wing AoAs. The most promising tonal noise attenuation occurs at $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$. At this relative phase angle, the effectiveness of tonal noise reduction does not significantly change with wing AoA sweeps, capable of providing around 12 to 15 dB reduction compared to the $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ case at all wing AoAs. For a relative phase angle of $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$, a similar level of tonal noise reduction to $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ is achieved at $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$. However, as the wing AoA increases, the effectiveness of tonal noise reduction at $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ decreases compared to the $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ case, with noise levels becoming comparable to those at $\Delta\psi = 45^\circ$. On the other hand, as J decreases to 0.35, as shown in the right column of Fig. 9, the relative phase angle of $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ yields nearly the same noise level as $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$. At higher wing AoAs, $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ provides almost no noise reduction compared to the $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ case. In contrast, both $\Delta\psi = 45^\circ$ and $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ provide greater noise reduction than the 0° phase configuration. At $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ achieves greater tonal noise reduction

Fig. 9 Directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise for different propeller relative phase angles, $\Delta\psi$, measured on the top arc for $J = 0.53$ (left column) and $J = 0.35$ (right column). Results are shown for (a) and (b) $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, (c) and (d) $\text{AoA} = 5^\circ$, (e) and (f) $\text{AoA} = 10^\circ$, and (g) and (h) $\text{AoA} = 15^\circ$.

Fig. 10 Directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise difference, ΔSPL , between $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ and $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ measured on the top arc for different AoAs. Results are shown for (a) $J = 0.53$ and (b) $J = 0.35$.

than $\Delta\psi = 45^\circ$ across all observer positions. However, as AoA increases, the effectiveness of tonal noise reduction for $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ gradually decreases. At AoA = 15° , $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ provides better noise reduction at observer positions $\theta < 75^\circ$, whereas $\Delta\psi = 45^\circ$ slightly outperforms $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ at larger observer angles.

Figure 10 presents a direct comparison of ΔSPL , defined as the 1st BPF tonal noise SPL difference of ($\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$) - ($\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$), at $J = 0.53$ and $J = 0.35$ across all four wing AoAs. At the higher propeller advance ratio of $J = 0.53$, the effectiveness of tonal noise reduction achieved with $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ is largely independent of both wing AoA and observer position along the microphone arc. At AoA = 0° , the reduction in 1st BPF tonal noise is marginally lower than that observed at the other wing AoAs, while the remaining cases exhibit nearly identical noise reduction characteristics. As J decreases to 0.35, it is observed that for upstream observer positions ($\theta < 70^\circ$), the noise reduction achieved by applying $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ remains similar across all four AoAs. However, for observer positions beyond $\theta = 70^\circ$, the effectiveness of tonal noise reduction reduces at higher AoAs, exhibiting reduced tonal noise reduction capability relative to the lower AoA conditions.

2. Tonal noise directivity on the horizontal arc.

Fig. 11 Directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise for different propeller relative phase angles, $\Delta\psi$, measured on the horizontal arc for $J = 0.53$ (left column) and $J = 0.35$ (right column). Results are shown for (a) and (b) AoA = 0° , (c) and (d) AoA = 5° , (e) and (f) AoA = 10° , and (g) and (h) AoA = 15° .

Figure 11 shows the tonal noise directivity curves at the 1st BPF at different propeller relative phase angles at $J = 0.53$ and $J = 0.35$ on the horizontal arc. At $J = 0.53$, for wing AoA $\leq 10^\circ$, $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ exhibits outstanding performance in tonal noise reduction capability compared to other relative phase angles. The noise reduction of applying any phase angle of $\Delta\psi < 45^\circ$ is marginal compared to the $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ case, especially at wing AoA = 0° . As the wing AoA increases from 0° to 10° , the SPL differences between $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ and $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ slightly increased for downstream observer positions $\varphi > 90^\circ$. However, when the wing further pitches to AoA = 15° , the effectiveness of applying 90° relative phase angle control drastically drops compared to lower AoAs. The right column of Fig. 11 shows the same concepts of tonal noise directivity at the lower advance ratio of $J = 0.35$. Similar to the high advance ratio case, tonal noise reduction for $\Delta\psi < 45^\circ$ is trivial compared to the $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ case. At this lower advance ratio, the effectiveness of applying 90° relative phase control to the two propellers enhances as wing AoA sweeps from 0° to 15° . The massive drop in noise-reduction effectiveness observed previously in the $J = 0.53$ case at AoA = 15° does not occur at this higher propeller rotational speed.

Figure 12 presents the directivity of the tonal noise difference, ΔSPL , at the first BPF between $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ and $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$, measured on the horizontal arc for all wing AoAs at $J = 0.53$ and $J = 0.35$. At $J = 0.53$, the noise reduction at AoA = 0° and 5° remains comparable at upstream observer positions ($\varphi < 90^\circ$), with reductions of approximately 18–22 dB. As the observer angle increases toward downstream locations, the curves gradually diverge, with AoA = 5° achieving slightly higher reductions, reaching around 22–24 dB near $\varphi \approx 100^\circ$. The case at AoA = 10° exhibits the highest overall noise reduction across the mid-range observer angles ($\varphi \approx 65^\circ$ – 100°), peaking at approximately 24–25 dB. In contrast, AoA = 15° produces the lowest reduction among all AoAs at upstream locations, with values as low as 7–10 dB, which is consistent with the previously observed increase in SPL for $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ at AoA = 15° (see Fig. 11(g)). However, this case shows a gradual improvement toward downstream angles, reaching approximately 15 dB. When the advance ratio decreases to $J = 0.35$, the behaviour changes notably. For AoA = 0° and 5° , the noise reduction remains relatively uniform across all observer positions, with values around 15–23 dB. Unlike the higher advance ratio case, increasing the wing AoA to 15° leads to a substantial enhancement in noise reduction, particularly for observer positions beyond $\varphi \approx 70^\circ$, where reductions reach up to approximately 28–30 dB. Similarly, AoA = 10° also demonstrates strong reductions, with peak values of around 30–32 dB near $\varphi \approx 75^\circ$. These results indicate that the effectiveness of phase-based noise reduction is strongly dependent on both advance ratio and inflow conditions, with higher AoA becoming beneficial at lower advance ratios, particularly in upstream observer regions.

Fig. 12 Directivity of the 1st BPF tonal noise difference, ΔSPL , between $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ and $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ measured on the horizontal arc for different AoAs. Results are shown for (a) $J = 0.53$ and (b) $J = 0.35$.

C. Numerical VPM results.

Figure 13 compares experimental measurements with numerical VPM predictions of the tonal noise directivity at the first BPF for AoA = 0° and 15° at $J = 0.53$. The relative phase angles considered in this study are $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ and 60° for the top arc, and $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ and 90° for the horizontal arc. These phase angles demonstrated the most promising noise reduction performance in the previous section and are therefore examined here to assess the predictive capability of the VPM simulations.

The VPM simulations capture the general trends of the tonal noise directivity patterns on both arcs. For the horizontal arc, the VPM predictions show good agreement with the experimental measurements in terms of both SPL magnitude and directivity shape across all observer positions at AoA = 0° for both relative phase angles. At AoA = 15° , the model tends to slightly overpredict the tonal noise levels at upstream observer positions ($\varphi < 90^\circ$) for $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$, while

Fig. 13 Comparison of experimental measurements (solid lines) and numerical VPM predictions (dashed lines) of 1st BPF tonal noise directivity on the top arc (left column) and horizontal arc (right column) for different relative phase angles, $\Delta\psi$, at $J = 0.53$. Results are shown for (a) and (b) $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, and (c) and (d) $\text{AoA} = 15^\circ$.

the agreement remains strong for $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$, with only minor discrepancies across the observer range. In contrast, larger discrepancies are observed for the top arc. At $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, the model consistently underpredicts the SPL by approximately 4 dB for $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$ and by around 10 dB for $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ across all observer positions. This underprediction becomes more pronounced as the AoA increases to 15° , particularly for $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$, where the differences between experimental and numerical results increase further. Despite capturing the overall directivity trends, the VPM appears to underestimate the strength of the acoustic sources on the top arc. This discrepancy is likely due to the limitations of mid-fidelity VPM modelling in capturing propeller asymmetric loading and inflow conditions under high wing AoAs , and may also be associated with a partial loss of wake coherence and under-resolved unsteady loading fluctuations, particularly in regions where propeller–propeller and wake–wing interaction effects become more relevant. These results suggest that while the VPM provides reliable qualitative predictions, further model refinement is required to improve quantitative accuracy under highly three-dimensional and distorted inflow conditions.

Figure 14 presents a comparison between experimental measurements and numerical VPM predictions of the first BPF tonal noise difference, ΔSPL , for $(\Delta\psi = 0^\circ) - (\Delta\psi = 60^\circ)$ on the top arc and $(\Delta\psi = 0^\circ) - (\Delta\psi = 90^\circ)$ on the horizontal arc at $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$ and 15° for $J = 0.53$. These ΔSPL results quantify the effectiveness of phase control and assess the capability of the VPM model in predicting tonal noise reductions. For the top arc (Fig. 14(a)), both experimental and numerical results show similar magnitudes and trends of noise reduction across the observer range. At $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, the measured noise reduction remains relatively uniform, with values of approximately 10–11 dB, while the VPM predicts slightly higher reductions of around 13–15 dB. At $\text{AoA} = 15^\circ$, both experimental measurements and VPM predictions achieve similar noise reduction levels of approximately 14–16 dB. This indicates that, despite the previously observed SPL offset, the VPM is able to reproduce the relative noise reduction between phase configurations with good accuracy along the top arc. For the horizontal arc (Fig. 14(b)), good agreement is observed between experiments and VPM predictions at downstream observer positions ($\varphi > 80^\circ$), where both approaches yield reductions of approximately 12–16 dB. However, larger discrepancies are evident at upstream locations ($\varphi < 80^\circ$). At $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, the experimental reduction decreases gradually from about 20 dB at $\varphi \approx 60^\circ$ to around 16 dB at $\varphi \approx 80^\circ$, whereas the VPM slightly overpredicts the reduction by approximately 2–4 dB in this region. This discrepancy becomes more pronounced at $\text{AoA} = 15^\circ$, where the experimental results show reductions as low as 8–10 dB at $\varphi \approx 60^\circ$, compared to VPM simulation values which overpredict the reduction magnitude to approximately 15–17 dB, resulting in a maximum difference of up to ~ 8 dB. In summary, the VPM model successfully captures the trends and relative differences in tonal noise reduction across phase configurations, particularly at downstream observer locations. However, the discrepancies

Fig. 14 Comparison of experimental measurements (solid lines) and numerical VPM predictions (dashed lines) of the 1st BPF tonal noise difference, ΔSPL , for different relative phase angles, $\Delta\psi$, at AoA = 0° and 15° with $J = 0.53$. Results are shown for (a) ($\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$) – ($\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$) on the top arc and (b) ($\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$) – ($\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$) on the horizontal arc.

at upstream positions and higher AoAs again suggest limitations in modelling complex inflow distortion and blade–wake interaction effects under highly non-uniform flow conditions.

V. Conclusions

This paper experimentally and numerically examines the aeroacoustic characteristics of a twin-propeller DEP system with propeller phase control under different wing AoAs. Two-bladed 9-inch propellers were mounted at the leading edge of a symmetric wing, and the wing AoA was varied from 0° to 15° to investigate noise emissions on the top and horizontal microphone arcs positioned around the wing. The experimental results show that, for both microphone arcs, the 1st BPF tonal noise directivity becomes less sensitive to changes in wing AoA as the propeller advance ratio, J , decreases for propeller relative phase angle of $\Delta\psi = 0^\circ$. Implementing propeller relative phase control is found to be effective in reducing the 1st BPF tonal noise emission of the DEP system for all advance ratios at different wing AoAs, although the level of attenuation is strongly dependent on observer position, propeller advance ratio, and wing AoA. In general, applying a relative phase angle of $\Delta\psi = 60^\circ$ for the top arc, and $\Delta\psi = 90^\circ$ for the horizontal arc, results in greater reductions in 1st BPF tonal noise SPL than other phase angles under most operating conditions.

The comparison between experimental measurements and numerical VPM predictions demonstrates that the model successfully captures the directivity trends and relative phase effects of 1st BPF tonal noise for both top and horizontal observer arcs at $J = 0.63$. Good agreement in tonal noise SPL is observed on the horizontal arc; however, VPM simulations systematically underpredict SPL on the top arc, with this discrepancy increasing slightly with wing AoA. Despite the offsets in absolute SPL, the model captures noise reduction trends well, consistent with experimental measurements. Based on these findings, future work should focus on detailed experimental and numerical investigations of the flow field around the propellers and wing at higher wing AoAs. Techniques such as hot-wire measurements and high-fidelity simulations would provide further insight into propeller–propeller and propeller–wing interaction effects under these highly inclined inflow conditions. A deeper understanding of these mechanisms would also enable targeted refinement of the mid-fidelity VPM framework, leading to more accurate and efficient predictions for noise analysis in future DEP system designs.

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References

- [1] Gohardani, A. S., “A Synergistic Glance at the Prospects of Distributed Propulsion Technology and the Electric Aircraft Concept for Future Unmanned Air Vehicles and Commercial/Military Aviation,” *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 57,

- 2013, pp. 25–70. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2012.08.001>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0376042112000735>.
- [2] Guan, S., Lu, Y., Su, T., and Xu, X., “Noise Attenuation of Quadrotor Using Phase Synchronization Method,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 118, 2021, p. 107018. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2021.107018>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1270963821005289>.
- [3] Lee, T., Ni, J., and Lin, G., “Aerodynamics and Flowfield of DEP Tiltwing During Transition with Deflected Trailing-Edge Flap,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 146, 2023, pp. 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4063934>.
- [4] Moore, K. R., and Ning, A., “Distributed Electric Propulsion Effects on Existing Aircraft Through Multidisciplinary Optimization,” *2018 AIAA/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference*, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2018-1652>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2018-1652>.
- [5] De Paola, E., Camussi, R., Stoica, G., Di Marco, A., and Capobianchi, G., “Aerodynamic and Aeroacoustic Experimental Investigation of a Three Propellers DEP Configuration,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 154, 2024, p. 109508. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2024.109508>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1270963824006394>.
- [6] Kim, H. D., Perry, A. T., and Ansell, P. J., “A Review of Distributed Electric Propulsion Concepts for Air Vehicle Technology,” *2018 AIAA/IEEE Electric Aircraft Technologies Symposium (EATS)*, 2018, pp. 1–21.
- [7] Ma, Y., Wang, C., Han, Z., and Wang, Y., “Mid-Fidelity Aero-Propulsive Coupling Approach for Distributed Propulsion Aircraft,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 157, 2025, p. 109859. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2024.109859>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S127096382400988X>.
- [8] Aref, P., Ghoreyshi, M., Jirasek, A., Satchell, M. J., and Bergeron, K., “Computational Study of Propeller–Wing Aerodynamic Interaction,” *AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, Vol. 5, No. 3, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/aerospace5030079>, URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2226-4310/5/3/79>.
- [9] Han, F., Lopes de Moraes Filho, L. F., Rezgui, D., Turhan, B. B., Azarpeyvand, M., Gautam, A., Zang, B., and Zhou, B., “Investigation of Aerodynamic and Aeroacoustic Performance of Various Distributed Electric Propulsion Configurations,” *AIAA Aviation Forum and Ascend*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2025-3644>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2025-3644>.
- [10] Gohardani, A. S., Doulgeris, G., and Singh, R., “Challenges of Future Aircraft Propulsion: A Review of Distributed Propulsion Technology and Its Potential Application for the All-Electric Commercial Aircraft,” *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 47, No. 5, 2011, pp. 369–391. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2010.09.001>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0376042110000497>.
- [11] Rizzi, S. A., Palumbo, D. L., Rathsam, J., Christian, A. W., and Rafaelof, M., “Annoyance to Noise Produced by a Distributed Electric Propulsion High-Lift System,” *23rd AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference*, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2017-4050>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2017-4050>.
- [12] Turhan, B. B., Jawahar, H. K., Rezgui, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Characterizing the noise patterns of overlapping propellers in forward flight,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol. 157, No. 4, 2025, pp. 2790–2801.
- [13] Zarri, A., Prenter, F. d., Avallone, F., Ragni, D., and Casalino, D., “Effects of Phase Synchronization on the Tonal Sound Directivity of Distributed Propellers,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol. 157, No. 5, 2025, pp. 3267–3281. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0036557>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0036557>.
- [14] Turhan, B. B., Jawahar, H. K., Rezgui, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Investigating the Aerodynamic and Aeroacoustic Behavior of a Single Propeller-Wing Configuration in Turbulent Flow,” *AIAA AVIATION FORUM AND ASCEND 2025*, 2025, p. 3146.
- [15] Lopes de Moraes Filho, L. F., Turhan, B. B., Franco, A., Trascinelli, L., Rezgui, D., Azarpeyvand, M., Ewert, R., Zhou, B., and Zang, B., “Assessment of Aeroacoustic Simulations for the Installation Noise of a Propeller-Wing Configuration in Forward Flight Using Multi-Fidelity Solvers,” *AIAA Aviation Forum and Ascend*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2025-3642>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2025-3642>.
- [16] Turhan, B. B., Jawahar, H. K., Bowen, L., Rezgui, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Aeroacoustic Characteristics of Distributed Electric Propulsion System in Forward Flight,” *AIAA Aviation Forum*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2023-4490>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2023-4490>.
- [17] Rizzi, S., Huff, D., Jr, D., Bent, P., Henderson, B., Pascioni, K., Sargent, C., Josephson, D., Marsan, M., He, H., and Snider, R., “Urban Air Mobility Noise: Current Practice, Gaps, and Recommendations,” *NASA*, 2020.

- [18] Zhao, C., Yang, Y., Cheng, Z., Zhang, T., and Liu, Y., “Recent advancements and challenges for eVTOL aircraft aerodynamic noise in Urban Air Mobility,” *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 161, 2026, p. 101184.
- [19] Combey, K., Elsayed, O. A., Magrini, A., Ramirez, F. N., Wang, S., Qaissi, K., Chouiyakh, H., Pereira, L. T., and Ragni, D., “Aerodynamic and aeroacoustic interactions in multirotor aircraft for urban air mobility: A review,” *Physics of Fluids*, Vol. 38, No. 1, 2026.
- [20] Turhan, B. B., Rezgüi, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Acoustic Effects of Differential Rotor Speeds on Twin-Propeller UAV System,” *Drones*, 2026.
- [21] Lee, H. M., Lu, Z., Lim, K. M., Xie, J., and Lee, H. P., “Quieter propeller with serrated trailing edge,” *Applied Acoustics*, Vol. 146, 2019, pp. 227–236.
- [22] Turhan, B. B., Jawahar, H. K., Gautam, A., Syed, S., Vakil, G., Rezgüi, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Acoustic Characteristics of Phase-Synchronized Adjacent Propellers,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol. 155, No. 5, 2024, pp. 3242–3253. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0025990>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0025990>.
- [23] Shao, M., Lu, Y., Xu, X., Guan, S., and Lu, J., “Experimental Study on Noise Reduction of Multi-Rotor by Phase Synchronization,” *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 539, 2022, p. 117199. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2022.117199>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022460X22003947>.
- [24] Pascioni, K. A., Rizzi, S. A., and Schiller, N., “Noise Reduction Potential of Phase Control for Distributed Propulsion Vehicles,” *AIAA Scitech Forum*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2019-1069>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2019-1069>.
- [25] Turhan, B. B., Lopes de Moraes Filho, L. F., Pullin, S., Zhou, B. Y., Jawahar, H. K., Gautam, A., Rezgüi, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Numerical and Experimental Analysis of Synchronized Propellers for Noise Mitigation,” *30th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference*, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2024-3237>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2024-3237>.
- [26] Patterson, A., Gahlawat, A., and Hovakimyan, N., “Propeller Phase Synchronization for Small Distributed Electric Vehicles,” *AIAA Scitech Forum*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2019-1458>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2019-1458>.
- [27] Zilei, Y., Han, F., Turhan, B. B., Rezgüi, D., Masoudi, E., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Modelling and Experimental Validation of Tonal Noise Directivity of Multiple Propellers in Phase-Synchronised Operation,” *Proceedings of the 332nd AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference*, Brussels, Belgium, 2026.
- [28] Turhan, B. B., Han, F., Yi, Z., Rezgüi, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Phase synchronisation control for acoustic reduction in overlapping DEP configurations,” *Proceedings of the 332nd AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference*, Brussels, Belgium, 2026.
- [29] Turhan, B. B., Rezgüi, D., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Phase Synchronisation for Tonal Noise Reduction in a Multi-Rotor UAV,” *Drones*, Vol. 9, No. 8, 2025, p. 544.
- [30] Visingardi, A., Barbarino, M., De Gregorio, F., Greco, L., Testa, C., Zaghi, S., Yin, J., Reboul, G., Cavalli, A., Granata, D., Abergó, L., Guardone, A., Zanotti, A., Bernardini, G., Poggi, C., Candeloro, P., Pagliaroli, T., Barakos, G., Qiao, G., Fausel, F., Keßler, M., and Muth, M., “Analysis of the Aeroacoustic Performance of Twin Propellers in Hover by Using the CIRA-Cusano Test Rig,” *50th European Rotorcraft Forum 2024*, 2024. URL <https://elib.dlr.de/206691/>.
- [31] Hanson, L., Yi, Z., Zang, B., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Rotor Noise in Non-Axial Inflow Conditions,” *Applied Acoustics*, Vol. 228, 2025, p. 110345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2024.110345>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0003682X24004961>.
- [32] Yi, Z., Zang, B., Masoudi, E., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Experimental Characterization of Phase-Explicit Noise of Tandem-Rotor in Edgewise Flight,” *AIAA Aviation Forum and Ascend*, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2025-3071>, URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2025-3071>.
- [33] Yi, Z., Turhan, B. B., Masoudi, E., and Azarpeyvand, M., “Experimental Noise Characterisation of Phase-Locked Tandem-Rotor in Edgewise Flight,” 2026. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Under Review.
- [34] Winckelmans, G. S., “Topics in vortex methods for the computation of three-and two-dimensional incompressible unsteady flows,” 1989.
- [35] Winckelmans, G., and Leonard, A., “Contributions to vortex particle methods for the computation of three-dimensional incompressible unsteady flows,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 109, No. 2, 1993, pp. 247–273.
- [36] Alvarez, E. J., and Ning, A., “Development of a vortex particle code for the modeling of wake interaction in distributed propulsion,” *2018 Applied Aerodynamics Conference*, 2018, p. 3646.
- [37] Farassat, F., “Derivation of Formulations 1 and 1A of Farassat,” Tech. rep., 2007.